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Between Power and Principle: The Neo-Neo Debate in the International Relations

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to analyze and compare the both international relations paradigms: Neorealism and Neoliberalism. In order to do so, will be debated the interpretations of the role of states in the international system and the different concepts of international society and international relations for those theories. Ultimately, these paradigms are somehow juxtaposed, which will allow a critical analysis of its principles and its main contributions to the Theory of International Relations.

Keywords

Neorealism, Neoliberalism, International Relations, State.

Introduction

Many prominent theorists of international relations opine that the debate between Neorealists and Neoliberal Institutionalists marks the significant debate which enlightens much of the field's scholarship. The Neo-Neo debate has dominated researchers' attention and has produced an amount of papers which claim for one or the other point or aim to merge the two theories. Though, can the Neo-Neo debate be said to progress theory in international relations field as a whole? Or does it rather inhibit theoretical advancement by dissembling major points of settlement as points of controversy?

After giving a brief framework of the characteristics of both theories, this article will scrutinize the Neo-Neo debate and will debated the interpretations of the role of states in the international arena with the purpose of making a judgment on the two dominant approaches' involvement to theoretical innovation within International Relations. Firstly, this article will underline the remarkable epistemological, methodological,

and ontological resemblances on which the two theories are based. Furthermore, the article will be evaluated how the theories' agreed understanding of anarchy catalyzes agreement on many aspects. Finally, this paper will highlight the principal disagreement between Neorealists and Neoliberal over the extent of clash and cooperation in the international arena.

The idealist-liberal proposal

The idealist-liberal thinking, as well as the current liberal paradigm has some influences in the Enlightenment period which gave the Idealist-liberals confidence in the effectiveness of the standard not only as a regulator of conduct of internal and external relationships among individuals, but also as a promoter of peace between sovereign states. Moreover, free trade and democracy were conceived as effective factors in promoting peace and development.

The central concern of the liberal doctrine is the freedom of the individual. Individual autonomy must be protected and extremely encouraged, so that society as a whole can progress. For liberals, the search for free individuals and the realization of their interests produces a positive social outcome, even if their motivation is selfish.

This perspective gives the man a `good nature` which makes social progress reachable. Therefore, is found in the human being an original moral disposition, although in fact dormant now, to become master of his evil principle. Thus, the bad human behavior can be explained by the bad influence of inadequate and corrupt institutions, besides disagreement between leaders, the main cause of wars.¹

According to the idealist-liberal doctrine, well-ordered societies, governed by fair institutions tend to be self-regulated. The consequence of this view is that the state is perceived as a necessary evil and a potential threat. Nevertheless, indispensable to ensure the protection against external threats and the effectiveness of domestic law...

The State, in its struggle for power, oppresses the society and is constantly undermining peace and promoting wars.

The international system is perceived by liberals and realists as anarchic and conflictual. However, the liberal tradition differs by not accepting this condition as immutable. Thus, it develops proposals grounded in free trade, democracy and institutions, with the aim of changing the international reality, making it less confrontational and more cooperative.

¹ Immanuel Kant, *Perpetuous Peace*. Porto Alegre, LP&M, 1997, p.40.

Liberal thinkers say there is an incompatibility between trade and war. Armed conflicts are very detrimental to domestic economic activity and cause the cessation of international trade. As deepened interdependence among nations, reciprocity would be taken as the basis for the relationship between states. Therefore, the broader understanding of the benefits of trade for society would cause the public opinion support for more peaceful external policies.

Another conception of idealist-liberal tradition is the relationship between democracy and peace.

Perhaps it's more difficult to take any decision leading to war in republics whose power is rooted in the representation of collective interests. It is part of the premise that individuals refute the conflict, because they don't want to endanger their lives. Thus, democratic societies seek to resolve their differences peacefully through international law, guided by reason and life protection interests, material well-being and freedom.

The international institutions were designed to act as mechanisms that provide the peaceful resolution of disputes.

The strengthening of international law and the creation of institutions that intermedicate the relations between States would balance the international system since they would mitigate its conflictual character due to the state of anarchy.

The World War I was an alert for the need to implement changes in the international system. The intervention of US President Woodrow Wilson (1856-1923), in international politics led to the implementation of liberal precepts. It was believed that the war was a result of some failure existing in the balance of power, which regulated the relations between the great powers. Thus, Wilson presented on January 8, 1918, a document that became known as the Fourteen Points Wilson. Despite of the normative character and unscientific aspects, this set of proposals previewed the creation of the League of Nations in 1919 and marked the prodrome of a period of efforts to achieve peace, by legal means, which lasted until 1939.

The realist criticism

The failure of the Versailles Treaty, the 1930 Crisis, the World War II and the subsequent polarization of the international system discredited the liberal theories of International Relations. The disregard of liberals towards the power struggle would have shown the huge gap between the desire for peace and prosperity and the conflictual reality of international relations. Consequently, over the years marked by the Cold War, the realist theory was considered by most analysts as the only able to express faithfully the fundamental aspects that gave meaning to international relations in all its dimensions.

Edward Hallett Carr was the first to formulate a realist critique of the liberal doctrine. In his book, *Twenty Years` Crisis 1919-1939*, published just before the Second World War, Carr introduced the debate in the area between idealistic or utopian and realists. He states that the utopian makes of the political theory a norm that the political practice needs to adjust. Therefore, the realist sees the political theory as a kind of codification of the political practice.²

The realist paradigm was based on the classical authors of political science. The concepts of intellectuals such as Thucydides, Machiavelli and Hobbes were adapted to the premises and principles of the realism of the twentieth century. After World War II, Hans J. Morgenthau took a decisive step to propose in *Politics Among Nations* the power encoding as the main pillar of the realist current. Emphasizing a negative perception of the human being, whose nature is determined by fear, prestige and ambition. The core elements of analysis are the state, anarchy, survival and power.

For realists, the central actor in international relations is the state. It is considered unitary, because it acts homogeneously and uniformly in the international system and rational, since it defends the national interest defined as the acquisition of power in the international level, while seeking simultaneously the lowest cost and the highest benefits. Anarchy is a beacon concept of the action of States in the international system.

The absence of a supreme and legitimate authority that can dictate the rules, interpret and implement them and punish those who do not obey makes prevail the `law of the strongest` in which only the fittest could survive. During the time men live without a common power able to keep them all in respect, they are in that condition which is called war. A war that is of every man against every man. The war doesn't consist only in battle, or in the act of fighting, but in that period of time during which the will to wage battle is sufficiently known.³

Realists reproduce this scenario described by Hobbes as the `state of nature` in international relations. Thus, the states are permanently fighting for survival and distrust each other, in a context of inexorable anarchy that permeates the international relations. The survival is defined as the supreme national interest and fundamental, that mobilizes all national capacities and transcends all other interests. Being the survival of the state similar to the individual, it compels political leaders to take decisions morally unacceptable if they were taken by private individuals. It can be inferred that any goal of the ruler can only be valid if it is not opposing or reducing the primary goal of survival. Thus, the state is seen as a depository of the right to self-preservation that overcomes the moral obligation, making the realization of their interests a moral end in itself.⁴

² Edward CARR. *The Twenty Years` Crises 1919 -1939*. Brasília: Editora Universidade de Brasília, 2001, p. 18.

³ Thomas Hobbes, *The Leviathan*, São Paulo: Martin Claret, 2004, p. 98.

⁴ Edward CARR. *The Twenty Years` Crises 1919 -1939*. Brasília: Editora Universidade de Brasília, 2001, p. 206.

Power is considered by realists as a central element of analysis of international relations. Power is the ability to influence the international system more than being influenced by it, constituting means to ensure the security and survival.⁵ The irrepressible seek for power makes the presence of the force mark the relationship of the actors in the international environment as they are compelled to constantly improve their security mechanisms (military, foreign policy, economic power), in order to overcome other states. Therefore, the political action is based on power. This implies in the autonomy of the political sphere in relation to other social spheres, so that the action of the states can be analyzed from the struggle between states for power.

During the Cold War, the Principles of Political Realism spread in the analysis of international relations. Elaborated by Morgenthau, these principles highlight the objective character of political realism and its direct link with a `pessimistic` evaluation of human nature (1st Principle), the central importance in the political realism of `interest` with the observation that this should not be understood as immutable (Principles 2 and 3); the perception of the moral issue in international relations, under the provision that the moral aspirations of a nation do not identify with the set of moral precepts which govern the political universe (Principles 4 and 5), and the autonomy of the political sphere as a research field of international phenomenas (Principle 6).⁶ Morgenthau's work claims a timelessness framework to the precepts of the political realism. Thus, this doctrine has positioned itself as having a special depth which gave it a greater understanding of reality.

The emergence of neorealism

The Classic Realism prevailed over other prospects until mid-1970. In this decade, there was a reaction against the traditional theoretical concepts, because they no longer reflected the international scenario. The period of distention between the United States and the Soviet Union, following the Missile Crisis (1962), the end of the Cold War without the outbreak of a direct conflict, the repudiation in the United States of the Vietnam War, and the petroleum crisis of 1973 in which poor countries have imposed their political and economic interests to strong countries, showed the limitations of classical perspectives to interpret the contemporary international system.

Furthermore, the growing importance of economic issues challenged the centrality of the state's role in the international relations. Transnational corporations, international organizations and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) have emerged as influential factors in the international arena, giving rise to critics to the realist doctrine.

⁵ WALTZ .K. *Origins of War in Neorealist Theory*, Journal of Interdisciplinary History, v. 18, 1988.

⁶ Hans MORGENTHAU. *Politics Among Nations*. Brasília: Editora Universidade de Brasília, 2003.

In this context, Kenneth Waltz sought to rescue the realism in the face of the criticism that proliferated. His work named *Theory of International Politics* (1979) represented a turning point in the development of models for the analysis of international relations. It marked the rise of neorealism or structural realism, a theoretical approach that sought to improve and refine the classic realism.

In developing the international political theory, neorealism preserves the essential principles of *realpolitik*, but means and ends are seen differently, as are causes and effects. For Morgenthau rational statesman pursuit to build progressive power and without interruption, seeing it as an end in itself, whereas Waltz conceives power as a potentially useful way, so that States are at risk if they have excessive or insufficient power. Thus, a prudent statesman will aspire only to have the necessary power to achieve their goals. Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that, in crucial situations, the state's concern won't be with power, but with the security.

In the neorealist perspective, international politics can only be understood if the effects of the structure are added to the traditional realism explanations. Waltz defines structure in three aspects: as an ordering principle, characteristic of its units and the distribution of capacity between them. The ordering principle in international relations is the anarchy. This is due to the absence of a sovereign authority that has the monopoly of the legitimate use of force, comparable to the Hobbesian state of nature. The units, for being functionally similar, have no analytical highlight. In international relations, they are characterized by the self-help system, that is, cannot rely on the other units to ensure their survival. Inserted in an anarchic system, the states must provide their own security. The distribution of capacities is defined as the balance of power or polarity. At the systemic level, what matters is not the power resources of each unity, but how these resources are distributed among them. For Waltz, there may be only two kinds of capacity distribution between the units: bipolar or multipolar. A bipolar system would be considered more stable since it would hinder the double game and non-declared alliances between states, making the international system more transparent.

In summary, the neorealism has a structural image of the international system, picturing their units according to its ordering. States are considered unitary actors, whose fundamental purpose is survival, and are the units of the structure. The essential feature of the international system structure is anarchy, so that changes occur only when there are variations in the number of great powers. Considering that Waltz discards the possibility of a unipolar structure, because it could be confused with a hierarchical structure, the only feasible change is of a bipolar system to a multipolar one.

The international structure exerts a pressure that restricts and imposes on the behavior of the units, surpassing the purposes internally generated by States foreign policy, when shaping the interaction between units.

Structural realism explains why different units behave similarly and, despite variables, produce results within estimates. The neorealist theory explains the behavior of states in downward⁷ logic that is, start from the systemic structure and the unit's position in the international system, to explain behaviors and outcomes. Thus, it only explains international results, but not specific external policies.

According to the neorealist perspective, competition and conflict between states arise directly from the anarchy condition. States should provide their own security, but threats, or the impression of threats are constant in an anarchic order. Concerns to identify potential dangers and react to them becomes a *modus vivendi*, because the relations between the actors are marked by the security dilemma, measures that ensure the protection of a state decreasing the safety of others. Therefore, the source of comfort to a state becomes a source of concern for others.

By emphasizing how the structures affect actions and results, the neorealism rejects the assumption that the lust for power, inherent in man, is the sufficient cause of war. It frames the causal link between the interactions of units with international results. So, in an anarchic domain, a state of war exists not only if all States are ambitious for power, but also if they only seek to ensure their own safety.

The elaboration of the neorealist perspective represent the adequacy of the precepts of classic realism to the changes in the international system. This tradition came to dominate the discussion of international relations, not only to present relevant interpretations to the international system, but also by raising sharp criticism.

The neoliberalism

The discredit that reached the liberal tradition after 1945 was associated with its inability to understand the factors that engendered both the Second World War and the Cold War. Rated by realistic as utopian, the liberalism began to have a peripheral role in the interpretation of international relations, because it was believed that its premises were disconnected from the international reality.

However, in the 1970s, the detente created the perception that traditional security issues, which dominated the international analysis during the Cold War, would lose importance in face of economic issues, such as development and interdependence. The petroleum crisis, which highlighted the incipient situation of dependence of developed countries in relation to commodities from developing ones, combined with the cost

⁷ WALTZ .K. *Origins of War in Neorealist Theory*, Journal of Interdisciplinary History, v. 18, 1988.

of the Vietnam War effort, which shook the world's largest economy, showed the relative decline of the influence of the great powers in international relations.

From this scenario, the interdependence of the issue gained prominence with the publication of works *Transnational Relations and World Politics* (1971) and *Power and Interdependence: World Politics in Transition* (1977), both co-edited by Robert Keohane and Joseph Nye. They argued about the impossibility to think the international system exclusively from the security angle, as did realists. The international economy had evolved to a stage where the power came to be exercised by the exclusive use of financial and trade mechanisms, without the need of extensive use of force. These factors gave rise to the emergence of non-state actors, as they played more relevant roles than the states in decisions such as investments, technology and media for instance.

In this context, the approach of interdependence emphasized the importance of international organizations to create favorable conditions for cooperation. For Keohane and Nye, although the interdependence can be a source of conflicts, through international organizations would be possible to manage them in order to allow states to enjoy the benefits of a more integrated international system. Thus, trying to demonstrate how international cooperation could be explained, covering the concrete conditions of the contemporary world politics, including the problems arising from power asymmetries.

The events of the 1980s, however, announced the end of the interdependence paradigm. The election of Ronald Reagan for president of the United States, which catalyzed the end of détente and caused the hardening of the bipolar conflict, undermined the interdependent postulates. While the analysis of the 1970s predicted the trend toward obsolescence of the nation-state, the decline in the use of military force and the irrelevance of security concerns, the next decade would refute the importance of international organizations as international system actors, since there were not concrete signs of changes towards an international system more interconnected and interdependent.⁸

The idealist-liberal doctrine needed therefore be renewed, to challenge the neorealist premises. In order to preserve the core of his theory, Keohane reviewed and reformulated its postulates. This review began with the acceptance of two realistic principles: the state was considered an unitary actor, and the international system anarchic. The standard set by Waltz imposed to rival theoreticians to face the challenge of formulating a theory that respected the boundary between internal and external, and therefore, explained international politics from a systemic perspective instead of a reductionist one.

⁸ NYE, J. *Neorealism and Neoliberalism*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1986.

The neoliberal theorists agreed with the international situation of uncertainty and insecurity generated by anarchy, though they differed in relation to the consequences of that state. For neorealists, the implication of anarchy is the adoption of survival strategies which result in the competition for power; to the neoliberals the lack of authority does not preclude cooperation between States. Despite the factor of actors being recognized as selfish, it is argued that the existence of common interests in a structural context propitious to interaction, can give rise to cooperation.

However, Neoliberalism conceives that, in anarchy, states cannot perform in the maximum their interests. Due to the lack of information, prevails the uncertainty about what will be the reaction of the actors to the foreign policy of a state. In a complex system, such as the international, the success of an individual strategy will depend on its interaction with the strategies adopted by other actors. The security dilemma was taken by neoliberals, but its implication is not necessarily the conflict, as it is in the realist prospect. The logic of anarchy, which condemns the states to a situation of eternal conflict, can be changed. Considering that the actors are rational, and that the problem is in the interaction environment, the solution to the dilemma lies in changing that environment to allow the actors to better calculate their opportunities and thus make decisions that best meet their interests.

Neoliberals authors argue to be possible to change this context of strategic interaction between states by the creation of institutions. They classify three basic functions performed by the institutions for the formation of preferences of actors: they can increase the flow of information, control the fulfillment of commitments and change expectations about the strength of agreements. The problem of opacity of intentions, interests and preferences of states would be mitigated by increasing the flow of informations. This measure would increase transparency in international relations, contributing to reduce the uncertainty that characterizes the anarchic environment. Conditions for the coordination of strategies that benefit all parties through cooperation would be then created.

The control of commitments fulfillment, through institutional monitoring mechanisms, reduces the risk of cheating, creating conditions for states to adopt cooperative strategies with an expectation of reciprocity from the other members. Furthermore, mechanisms designed to penalize States that do not comply with agreements increase the cost of non-cooperative strategies, functioning as a way to compel them to `play by the rules of the game`. By changing the expectations of actors regarding the solidity of the agreements, decreases the lack of clarity about how they will behave during the process of interaction.

Thus, the existence of rules and procedures increases the predictability of international relations, and hence, the international security.

The neoliberalism not only recognizes the international anarchy as a source of conflict, as realists do, but also propose ways to make international relations more friendly. This theory discards the assumptions considered by realists as ingenuous as the unshakeable belief in progress from the reason, and part of an empirical analysis of the international system to provide an optional view to neorealist skepticism about the role of institutions in world politics.

The debate between paradigms

The theoretical contiguity between Neorealism and Neoliberalism is resumed to the design of international structure, combined with the perception of the state as an unitary actor and the international system as anarchic. Aside from this convergence, the paradigms are highlighted in the academic debate about the Theory of International Relations, for their differences.

The neoliberal criticism condemns the limitations of neorealist perspective. An important reason for the limits of Structural Realism is the fact that social recognition or authorization adds or reduces the actor material capabilities. In democratic regimes, the State's actions need to be legitimized by society, shaping the foreign policy strategies of states to endogenous interests of the country.⁹

The action of the State, for neorealists, is based on the maximum satisfaction of self-interest, and its behavior is contingently coordinated by the international structure. Critics of Realism, however, argue that is the state action based on implicit or explicit consensus on norms that helps coordinate the action. In this sense, the creation of international organizations is a choice of States to mitigate the consequences of international anarchy.

Neoliberals have a perception of the State which differs considerably from the theoretical perspective of neorealists. While these disregard reciprocity between international relations and internal contradictions of countries, those believe that the state is not artificially separated from the social structure which he relates.

The realist tradition denies the relevance of the differences between the individual units, they are guided only by self-interest and the international structure. Thus, the state resembles a "billiard ball", opaque and standardized, so that their social peculiarities, idiosyncrasies and historical formation does not alter its performance in the international system.

⁹ KATZENSTEIN, P. *Analyzing Changes in International Politics*. Federal Republic of Germany: 1990, p. 8.

The neoliberal paradigm, while recognizing the influence of the state of anarchy in the actions of the actors, does not reject the importance of endogenous factors to the States in international politics. It differentiates government from state, which, in turn, is not conceived ``a-historically``. So, Neoliberalism does not take the risk of universalizing a voluntarist policy conception in an atomized society.

Represented by Waltz, Neorealism criticizes the neoliberal postulates for the lack of historical perspective. Liberal ideas have been accepted only from 1919, the year that was established the creation of the League of Nations. On the other hand, he claims that neorealism has an "ahistorical" approach, considering permanent system features that are the product of distinct and specific phases of international relations.

However, even the most abstract theoretical discourse and scientific developments are the products of private societies in a particular historical period. Furthermore, the assumption that there has been an "international system" before formation of nation-states or the emergence of the international market is questionable.

The realist theory could never satisfactorily answer how states define their interests and how these interests change. Realists argue that the actors learn to respond to structural changes in their environment, adopting cooperative strategies only when there are mutual benefits. This explanation can often answer satisfactorily the international scenario, but it is incomplete because it does not clarify how the interests are formulated or redefined. Different geopolitical situations can evoke different reactions, depending on the ruler or dominant ideology in a state. The realist theory neither interprets how groups of a society can abandon partners in transnational coalitions or use norms and international organizations to advance or retard the learning of new interests for their own government. Thus, the realist theory is better at explaining interactions than interests. An interest theory defined only in terms of power is a theory of impoverished interests.¹⁰

Another debate that polarized neorealists and neoliberals concerns relative gains versus absolute gains. Neorealists claim to be the gain of perception, in a state, due the comparison with other actors. State actions, in the international system, would be guided by the gains that can be obtained more than other countries, with the aim of preserving the status quo or surpass their pairs. For neoliberals, this logic can and should be changed so that states can only crave for absolute gains. This would stimulate the interaction between the actors, making international relations less competitive and more cooperative.

Carr criticizes liberal precepts that urge for a cooperative and unified world. As well as appeals for "national solidarity" in domestic politics, always start from a dominant group, that can use this solidarity to strengthen its control of the nation as a whole, appeals for international solidarity and world unity start from dominant

¹⁰ NYE, J. *Neorealism and Neoliberalism*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1986, p.160.

nations, which hope to exercise control over an unified world. The calls¹¹ for solidarity are analogous to international appeals for international cooperation. Unequivocally, the current herald of liberal theories is the dominant power, the United States.

Ultimately, both the neoliberal paradigm as the neorealist have addictions. On the one hand, the neoliberal belief in institutions as cooperation agents promoters can be classified as naive, because in the current scenario, international organizations reflect the distribution of power in the international system. On the other hand, Neorealism excludes four essential ingredients of all effective political thought: a finite goal, an emotional appeal, the right of moral judgment and a field of action.

Conclusion

Neorealism and Neoliberalism represent an evolution of the idealist-liberal and realistic theories. The theoretical debate about the international relations followed the changes in the international system, which, as it becomes more complex, requires the adaptation of the theory to the reality. Neorealism managed to revitalize the realist theory, creating the concept of structure and systematizing realistic assumptions, which was mostly made by Waltz's work. The analysis rooted in power and survival is essential in any international event, but incurs errors when excludes other variables that influence the action of States. Represented by Nye and Keohane, Neoliberalism, on the other hand, has become more plausible adopted realist assumptions, as the central role of the state in international relations and the state of anarchy and objectively analyze the international system. However, this paradigm inherited utopian elements of idealism-liberal because it attempts to change international relations through cooperation between the actors. In this diapason, the emphasis on the importance of international organizations as promoters of peace forgets the policy behind the creation of these institutions. Therefore, the idealist liberal traditions and realist provide a meaningful analysis of international policy only if used with complementarity. This relationship gives the Theory of International Relations a unified nature, because the paradigms that compose it are exclusionary, but complementary, thus entailing more solid interpretations of the international system.

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